

PECULIARITY OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS OF THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE REFLECTING CULTURAL AND SPIRITUAL VALUES

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Abstract. Phraseological units play a special role in creating a linguistic picture of the world. The meaning of phraseological units is closely related to the background knowledge of native speakers, the personal experience of a person, and the cultural traditions of the people. Phraseological units ascribe to objects signs associated with the world picture, evaluating it, expressing an attitude to it. That is why, speaking about phraseological units, they often note their national originality, since each language has its own phraseology. The phraseological composition of the language is a direct component of the culture of the people, reflecting the features of its spiritual warehouse. Phraseological units act as a means of reflecting the world, they absorb mythological, religious, ethical ideas of peoples of different eras and generations.

Key words: phraseological unit, prototype, linguistics, culture, tradition, religion,

The English language has a very rich phraseology. It reflects the peculiarity of the way of life, culture and mentality of the people. In English, there are a large number of phraseological units associated with the traditions, mythology and religion. The facts of the country's history, geography and economy are widely represented in the meaning and component composition of many phraseological units.

Many researchers note that a large layer of phraseology in each language arises precisely on a national basis. In the formation of phraseological units, linguistic and extralinguistic factors play a role, which belong to the field of history of the people speaking a given language [1; 2]. At the same time, there is a continuous

accumulation of sociocultural experience, which is reflected in the system of phraseological fund of the language.

To approach phraseology as a keeper and source of socio-cultural information, it is necessary to distinguish between the phraseological unit itself and its prototype, under which the variable combination of words is called, which has become the basis of phraseological rethinking. As noted by V.N. Thelia in her research, under the secondary lexical nomination, should be understood as the use of nominative means existing in the language in a new naming function for them [3]. The specificity of the phraseological unit as a sign of the secondary nomination lies in the fact that as a result of the secondary nomination, a semantic transformation of the component composition of the variable combination of words occurs, the result of which is a new phraseological unit that performs the function of fixing, storing and transmitting information about the history, way of life, traditions, morals and culture of the people [4]. Metaphor is one of the main ways of semantic transformation of the primary meanings of phraseological units.

The main property of the phraseological unit as a result of the secondary nomination is imagery, which is associated with the spiritual culture of this linguistic community and thus testifies to its experience and traditions. The imagery of phraseological units is manifested in the semantics of phraseological units as a result of seeing two pictures caused by primary and secondary nomination. At the same time, it is important to note that the uniqueness of the images that are used as the basis for the rethinking of phraseological units, and the associations that caused a particular image in the minds of speakers, has a national and cultural specificity.

Let's look at examples.

He stuttered slightly. "Why? Why?"

I muttered:

"I have to find out about this..."

"Indeed". Even his nostrils turned white. "Well, sir, let us not beat about the bush. You will abandon it at once" [5].

The origin of the meaning of the phraseological unit "to beat about the bush" - "ходить вокруг да около" is associated with the children's game "mulberry bush", which resembles a round dance (хоровод). At the same time, the game is accompanied by the chorus "Here we go round the mulberry bush".

And then Charles Tansley became as nice as he could possibly be. He began playing ducks and drakes [6].

The phraseological unit "to play ducks and drakes with something" meaning "to sharpen something; recklessly do anything" is the source of information about the children's game, which consisted in throwing flat pebbles on the surface of the water. Subsequently, this phraseological unit received the meaning of "to squander their money".

Phraseological units created by people engaged in various fields of activity and sports, being brief, colloquial and metaphorically reinterpreted, are used in expressive speech.

Clyde was irritated by the certain types of men: down-and-out labours, loafers, drunkards, wastrels, the botched and helpless who seemed to drift in, because they had no other place to go. And always his parents were saying "Glory to God" and taking collections for the legitimate expenses of the hall [7].

The special expressiveness of the English phraseological unit "down-and-out", which is used in the sense of "ruined people; thrown overboard life", is created by means of reception - a regular combination of two certain words.

Metaphorically, many phraseological expressions related to military affairs were reinterpreted, which entered the colloquial English language, such as the phraseological unit "to stand one's ground" with the meaning "to stand your ground, to remain true to your own beliefs, principles."

And Clyde was so tortured by the fear of what was about to befall him in case he submitted to Roberta and did not stand his ground [7].

In English, phraseological units associated with the sea are especially numerous, which stem from the island thinking of the British, from the past life of the nation, hanging from the maritime space surrounding the islands of Great Britain. *I was half afraid to show it to the gentleman who had spoken to me about it. Imagine my surprise when he said it was a masterpiece, and offered me thirty thousand francs. I dare say he would have paid more, but frankly, I was so taken aback that I lost my head; I accepted the offer before I was able to collect myself [8].*

The meaning of the phraseological unit "taken aback" is derived from its original meaning when referring to sails suddenly pressed against the mast by a wind. It should be noted that in this example, the phraseological expression "I lost my head" is also used in the sense of "confused".

This picture is now in the National Gallery at Stockholm. The Swede is adept at the gentle pastime of fishing in troubled waters [8].

The phraseological unit "to fish in troubled waters" is part of the proverb "It is good fishing in troubled waters", which, in turn, was borrowed from the French language.

Julia got the notes from Tom but she could not make head or tail of it [9].

Thus, the structure of the phraseological unit "to be unable to make head or tail of something" with the meaning "not to understand what is what" includes the name of monetary units (head - the front side of the coin, tail - the reverse side of the coin).

"My aunt has often spoken to me about you. You are one of her favorites, and I am afraid, one of her victims also".

"I am in Lady Agatha's black books at present", answered Dorian, with a funny look of penitence. "I promised to go to a club in Whitechapel with her last Tuesday, and I really forgot all about it [10].

It should be emphasized that phraseological units with the name of color in English are associated with linguistic and extra linguistic factors: with traditions and customs, religion and culture, mythology and history. The meanings of

phraseological units with the name of the color are determined by the socio-historical, national and cultural experience of this language collective. The phraseological unit "to be in a person's black books", meaning "to be in a bad account with someone", came to the English language in the XVII century. "Black Book" is a book in black binding, which recorded violations by clergy in the monasteries of the XVII century.

Evvy had to confess that he needed some Dutch courage rather badly [11].

It should be noted that the "Dutch" component introduces a negative connotation into the phraseological unit "Dutch courage", meaning "bravery in hops". This is due to the negative associations of the British regarding Anglo-Dutch competition on the seas and wars in the seventeenth century.

"Oh", she said with an accent of comprehension, though secretly his speech had been so much Greek to her and she was wondering what a "left" was [12].

The lexeme "Greek", used in the structure of the phraseological unit "to be Greek to somebody", was traditionally used in English in the sense of "incomprehensible, alien", which, in turn, became the basis for the formation of the meaning of this phraseological unit - "Chinese literacy" - "something completely incomprehensible, which is very difficult to understand".

And he remembered the many evenings he and his fellows had in his salad days [13].

The plays of W. Shakespeare became the source of English phraseology. Thus, the phraseological expression "one's salad days", which has the meaning "young years", entered the English language from the work of W. Shakespeare "Antony and Cleopatra".

Bible translations have had a very big impact on the English language. For centuries, the Bible was the most widely read book in England. Numerous phraseological expressions entered the English language from the pages of the Bible. *Clyde was taken by those people and with what purpose? He had no money, he was as poor as a Church mouse compared to them and moreover he got his job by the*

skin of his teeth. ... And Clyde took heart as he occasionally came across the name of a person of his own age who had a store in Lyaugus and who could help him [7]. Jimmie: “What do you want to go and hamper yourself with a man who’ll always be a millstone round your neck” [9].

Biblical images and concepts have been preserved in the following phraseological expressions: as poor as a church mouse – very poor; those skin of one’s teeth– barely, miraculously; then take heart – to perk up, not to lose heart, to be inspired; then be a millstone round smb's neck - to be a stone on someone's neck.

To sum up, the phraseology of the English language is distinguished by national identity, as well as is an important source of socio-cultural information about the country of the studied language. Extra linguistic factors involved in the formation of phraseological units of the English language determine the national identity of its phraseology.

The national-cultural component is an integral part of the structure of the meaning of the phraseological unit due to the fact that phraseological units are based on a different representation that arises in the minds of representatives of a particular linguistic and cultural community. Cultural events, sports, everyday life, customs, beliefs and behavior of people, their attitude to the surrounding world and each other are reflected in the phraseology of the English language. Phraseological units store and transmit information about the norms, values and social foundations of society.

In English, phraseological units are frequent, the prototypes of which are historical events, as well as geographical locations. Such phraseological expressions contain a bright national-cultural component in their semantics. When studying the national and cultural features of the phraseological units of the English language, it is important to take into account cultural attitudes, religious truths, as well as views and beliefs existing in society.

REFERENCES

1. Molotkov A.I. Basics of the phraseology of the Russian language. [Osnovy frazeologii russkogo jazyka]. Leningrad: Nauka, 1977. 283 p. (in Russ.)
2. Domashnev A.I. Modern German language in its national variants. [Sovremennyj nemeckij jazyk v ego nacional'nyh variantah]. Leningrad: Nauka, 1983. 231 p. (in Russ.)
3. Telia V.N. The types of language values. [Tipy jazykovykh znachenij]. Moscow: Nauka, 1981. 298 p. (in Russ.)
4. Galdabini S.V., Fedorenkova T.N. The role of classical and Christian culture in the study of the phraseology of modern English. [Rol' antichnoj i hristianskoj kul'tury v izuchenii frazeologii sovremennogo anglijskogo jazyka]. Cultural aspects of Russian education: theory, problems, experience of implementation: proc. nauch.-practical use. Conf. Tyumen state University, 1996. P. 62-64. (in Russ.)
5. Cronin A.J. Shannon's way. London: Gollancz, 1958. 303 p.
6. Woolf V. To the lighthouse. Ringwood (Vic.): Penguin books, 1971. 306 p.
7. Dreiser Th. An American tragedy. New York: New American library, 2000. 859p.
8. Maugham W.S. The moon and sixpence. London: Heinemann, 1982. 252 p.
9. Maugham W.S. Theatre. Moscow: Manager, 1997. 300 p.
10. Wilde O. The picture of Dorian Gray. Cleveland, New York: The World publishing company, 1945. 186p.
11. Murdoch I. The sandcastle. Chatto and Windus: Penguin books, 1964. 312 p.
12. London J. Martin Eden. New York: Macmillan, 1957. 381 p.
13. Galsworthy J. In chancery. New York: Scribner, 1920. 373 p.